

Synthesis of strong SiV photoluminescent diamond particles on silica optical fiber by chemical vapor deposition*

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ABSTRACT: The separated silicon-vacancy (SiV) photoluminescent diamond particles were synthesized on silica optical fiber by hot filament chemical vapor deposition (HFCVD). The effects of pre-treated method and chamber pressure on the microstructure and photoluminescence of diamond particles are investigated. The results show that diamond particles are homogeneously distributed on the surface of optical fiber, which is dip-coated into the slurry consisting of nanodiamond particles for 2-5 minutes. With chamber pressure increasing from 1.6 to 3.5 kPa, the shape of particles transits from flake to circle, while diamond particles cannot be deposited on the fiber with pressure further increasing to 4.5 kPa. The samples synthesized under 2.5 kPa chamber pressure are composed of diamond particles with size around 200-400 nm, exhibiting stronger SiV photoluminescence with the width of around 6 nm.

Keywords: diamond, silicon vacancy, photoluminescence, optical fiber

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1. Introduction

Single photon source is critical for quantum information processing and quantum communication^[1]. The ideal single photon source generates exactly one photon at a time and all photons are identical. As a result, if any two photons were sent through separated arms of a beam-splitter, they can produce full interference. For the application in quantum communication, the most widely used single photon source is

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generated from nonlinear optics or emitted by two-level systems such as quantum dot and color centers in diamond. The nonlinear optics is not “real” single photon source which follows the Poisson distribution^[2]. The quantum dot such as InAs quantum dot only works well under 10K^[3]. Color centers in diamond such as nitrogen vacancy (NV) center^[4,5], nickel-nitrogen (NE8) center^[6], Cr-related center^[7] and silicon vacancy (SiV) center^[8–10] are highly photostable at room temperature.

The single photon source is generally obtained by coupling single photons into optical fibers, which are compatible with the current fiber communication network. There are various methods to achieve this integration of single photon source with optical fiber. Schroder et al^[11] picked the NV center contained diamond particles onto the optical fiber through the atomic force microscope (AFM) cantilever tip. Scientists^[12] also directly doped the NV diamonds into the tellurite glass, which had potentially high collection efficiency but increased the risk of damaging the color centers. Rabeau et al^[13] directly deposited NV diamond particles on fiber endface and achieved fluorescence waveguiding. Besides that, scientist^[14,15] integrated the CdSe Colloidal quantum dots with microfiber and achieved single photon waveguide.

The SiV center in diamond exhibits many extraordinary photon properties than NV center, such as high degree of photons polarization and short life time^[16]. Recent work indicated that the single SiV centers exhibited very high fluorescence counts, suggesting that it could be an efficient photon source for quantum communication application^[17]. Kunuku et al^[18] prepared ultrananocrystalline diamond particles with the size of about 1 μm with SiV fluorescence, which formed nearly continuous films on soda-lime glass fiber by using microwave plasma chemical vapor deposition (MPCVD) method. The samples exhibited a relatively strong intensity of SiV fluorescence but a wide zero photon line of about 9.4 nm width. To realize the possibility of coupling single photons of the SiV diamonds into the optical fiber, separated diamond particles deposited on the fiber surface are required.

In this paper, we prepared individual diamond particles on the surface of the fibers and investigate the impact of deposition conditions on the photoluminescence and microstructural properties of diamond particles. **Seeding is a key parameter**^[19,20]

that can strongly affect diamond CVD growth process on various substrates^[20,21]. The dip-coating^[22] by low concentrated nanodiamond suspension was used to coat individual diamond nanoparticles onto the fiber surface. The effects of different seeding times on the structural and photoluminescent properties of diamond particles have been discussed. In addition, the chamber pressure was found to be another important parameter for the growth of diamond particles and fabrication of SiV center, while there are few reports about the related studies.

In this paper, the effects of pre-treatment method and chamber pressure on diamond quality and SiV photoluminescent property are well studied. The results show that chamber pressure of 2.5 kPa is superior for the growth of SiV photoluminescent diamond particles with size around 200-400 nm, exhibiting stronger SiV photoluminescence with the width of around 6 nm.

2. Experiment methods

Standard silica single mode optical fiber with the polymer protection etched in nitric acid was selected in the experiments. The fiber was 2-cm-long with a diameter about 125 μm . The fiber was dipped in acetone and deionized water for 5 minutes respectively, to remove the remaining acid. After cleaning, the optical fiber was seeded with nanodiamond in diamond/Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) & dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) solution to improve the diamond nucleation rates. The solution was prepared in two steps. First, 0.2 g PVA was dissolved in 20 g DMSO while ultrasonic was carried out under 80 °C water. After the PVA/DMSO dropwise cooled to room temperature, 0.1g nanodiamond powders (average size around 100 nm) to form the seeding slurry. The seeding time is set as 0, 2, 5 and 15 minutes, named as T0, T2, T5 and T15, respectively. After that, the optical fiber was cleaned in deionized water and acetone before being loaded into the reaction chamber.

The diamond particles were synthesized using the hot filament chemical vapor deposition (HFCVD) system. The filament power was kept at 1.7 kW, the relative concentration ratio of components of the gas mixture was acetone: hydrogen = 1:5. The pressure of the gas mixture in the reaction chamber was set as 1.6, 2.5, 3.5 and 4.5 kPa, respectively. The deposition time was fixed to 20 minutes according to our

previous study. The efficient creation of SiV centers is attributed to the plasma etching of the fiber substrate.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (TESCAN VAGA3) measurements were performed to investigate the morphology of diamond particles on the fiber surface. Their microstructure and composition were examined by visible Raman spectroscopy. The presence of the SiV photoluminescence on diamond endface was confirmed using PL spectroscopy. Raman and PL spectra of the diamond particles were collected on deposition side using a Raman/PL spectrometer (HORIBA HR800) with 514 nm excitation laser.

3. Results and Discussion

Fig. 1 shows the surface morphology of the diamond particles synthesized on fiber surface under 1.6 kPa chamber pressure after different seeding times of 0, 2, 5 and 15 minutes, which is named as 1.6T0, 1.6T2, 1.6T5 and 1.6T15, respectively. For the sample without seeding, the SEM graph indicates that there is only the contamination on fiber surface. The SEM graphs also exhibit that flake-shape structures appear for all the seeded samples, and the flake-shape particles with inhomogeneous size are disorderly distributed on fiber surface. With seeding time extending to 15 minutes, the flake tends to connect with each other and forms a continuous diamond film. It is indicated that the seeding time of 2 minutes prefers to prepare the separated particles in the case of 1.6 kPa chamber pressure.

Fig. 2(a) shows the PL spectra of diamond particles deposited under 1.6 kPa after different seeding times. SiV photoluminescent peak is not observed in the PL spectra of 1.6T0 and 1.6T2 seeded samples. However, there is a relatively weak SiV photoluminescence peak appeared at about 738 nm in the PL spectra for the samples 1.6T5 and 1.6T15. The position of SiV zero photon line (ZPL) is at 738.7 nm, which is slightly red-shifted than the ideal SiV center ZPL. The full width at half maximum (FWHM) of SiV ZPL is about 9 nm at room temperature. The intensity ratio of the SiV ZPL to the peak at 552 nm (diamond Raman signal) characterizes the normalized intensity of the SiV ZPL. The normalized intensity of SiV ZPL is 0.52 and 0.35 for samples 1.6T5 and 1.6T15, respectively. This suggests that sample 1.6T5 has stronger

SiV ZPL intensity.

The corresponding visible Raman spectra were collected to analyze the composition of samples at room temperature and fitted with six Gaussian peaks, as shown in Fig. 2(b). The Raman spectra show that the samples 1.6T0 and 1.6T2 exhibit the high contents of graphite and amorphous carbon, while no diamond phase is observed. This suggests that short seeding time causes low nucleation rates, leading to poor diamond quality and the absence of SiV photoluminescence. The samples 1.6T5 and 1.6T15 display a strong diamond peak at about 1330 cm^{-1} , which is slightly blue shifted about 2 cm^{-1} compared with the ideal diamond peak in Raman spectrum. The fitted diamond contents calculated by using the equation in reference^[9,23] are 74% and 76% for samples 1.6T5 and 1.6T15, respectively. The peaks at about 1140 and 1470 cm^{-1} are due to the reflection of the trans-polyacetylene (TPA)^[24-27], which is related to hydrogen in amorphous carbon grain boundaries (GBs) of the diamond particles. The Raman spectra have two large bands at 1350 and 1560 cm^{-1} called D and G peak attributed to sp^2 -bonded carbon^[28,29], the G peak is related graphite specifically. The fitted TPA contents are 9.6% and 7.4% for samples 1.6T5 and 1.6T15, respectively.

Comparing the PL and Raman spectra of samples 1.6T5 and 1.6T15, we find that these samples have a strong diamond peak, but weak SiV ZPL. The Raman spectra indicate that samples synthesized under 1.6 kPa mainly consist of TPA, graphite and diamond, thus forming a flake-shape structure, as shown in SEM morphology. The high contents of TPA, which is related to hydrogen in amorphous carbon in GBs, quench the SiV luminescence^[9]. Besides that, the existence of graphite has a major influence on photoluminescence. For NV center in diamond, it was proved that the existence of energy transferred from an NV center to a graphene monolayer and then resulted in weaker fluorescence^[30]. Here, the graphite contents of samples 1.6T5 and 1.6T15 are 13.5% and 4.1%, which significantly decreases the photoluminescence intensity of SiV.

To decrease the contents of the amorphous carbon and TPA in the particles, we increased the chamber pressure to 2.5 kPa. Fig. 3 shows the surface morphologies of the diamond particles synthesized on the surface of fiber under 2.5 kPa with 20

minutes deposition time. Their seeding time is 0, 2, 5 and 15 minutes, respectively, which is named as 2.5T0, 2.5T2, 2.5T5 and 2.5T15. For the sample 2.5T0, the SEM graph indicates that there is only contamination on fiber surface. For the samples 2.5T2, 2.5T5 and 2.5T15, the diamond particles are round shaped with size of 200-400 nm. The well-separated diamond particles are obtained with the seeding time of 2 and 5 minutes. Comparing to the morphology of the samples synthesized under 1.6 kPa in Fig. 1, we find that synthesized diamond particles are more homogeneously distributed on the fiber under 2.5 kPa chamber.

Fig. 4(a) shows the PL spectra of samples synthesized under 2.5 kPa with different seeding times. The samples exhibit stronger SiV ZPL except for the sample without nanodiamond seeding. The normalized intensity of SiV ZPL is 2.8, 1.6 and 1.3 for the samples 2.5T2, 2.5T5 and 2.5T15, respectively. Comparing with samples synthesized under 1.6 kPa, we find that the chamber pressure under 2.5 kPa improves the SiV PL intensity of the diamond particles. The SiV ZPL positions for all samples are red-shifted from the theoretical SiV ZPL position (738 nm) by less than 1 nm, which indicates the existence of internal lattice stress and the surrounding components like graphite and TPA^[24,25]. The FWHM of SiV ZPL is around 5.8 to 8 nm at room temperature. Thus, higher chamber pressure enhances the number of the SiV centers and decreases the FWHM value of SiV ZPL.

Fig. 4(b) shows the corresponding Raman spectra of the samples seeded with different time under 2.5 kPa. Raman spectra indicate that all samples have a weak diamond peak at 1332 cm^{-1} and two TPA peaks at 1140 and 1470 cm^{-1} . Comparing with the Raman spectra in Fig. 2 (a) and Fig. 4 (a), we find that samples synthesized under different chamber pressures exhibit different diamond composition. The diamond contents are 40.3%, 72%, 71% and 76% with the TPA contents of 24.7%, 4.3%, 6.3% and 6.0%, for the samples 2.5T0, 2.5T2, 2.5T5 and 2.5T15, respectively, indicating a massive non-diamond phase in the samples without SiV peaks. These contents cover diamond grains, thus quenching the excitation of SiV photon. For the samples with SiV photoluminescence, their Raman spectra all exhibit high diamond contents and low TPA contents. The graphite contents are 6.6%, 9.2%, 9.3% and 6.0%

for the samples 2.5T0, 2.5T2, 2.5T5 and 2.5T15, respectively. The sample seeded for 15 mins exhibits similar composition with the sample seeded for 5 mins but with larger background noise.

Above results show that under 2.5 kPa, the particles have higher diamond content and stronger SiV PL intensity. The effects of chamber pressure on diamond deposition and SiV fabrication can be attributed to two factors. First, the concentration of hydrogen active groups increases with increased pressure^[31,32]. The lifetime of hydrogen active groups is much longer than CH₃ active group, and the CH₃ active group is sensitive to the chamber pressure^[33]. Second, the concentration of hydrogen atoms was reduced with reduced pressure^[34]. Therefore, the ratio of CH₃ groups to H groups on substrate increases with the decreased chamber pressure. In addition, the SEM graphs in Fig. 1 and Fig. 3 indicate that the shape of the synthesized diamond particles transmitted from the flake-shape structure to spherical-shape when chamber pressure was increased to 2.5 kPa.

Comparing the PL spectra and the corresponding Raman spectra in Fig. 4(b), we find that the sample without seeding has a weak diamond peak and it does not exhibit SiV photoluminescence. The photoluminescence of SiV is quenched by the high dense graphite phase^[30,35]. The diamond peak positions for 1.6 and 2.5 kPa synthesized samples are slightly shifted about 1 cm⁻¹ comparing with ideal diamond^[36]. This indicates that the synthesized diamond grains exhibit excellent quality and minimum internal stress. The samples synthesized at different pressures exhibit similar diamond quality but different diamond contents. This is consistent with other researchers' results that the lower pressure is favorable for diamond nucleation but adverse for diamond growth^[37,38]. Combining the PL spectra, Raman spectra and SEM graphs, we conclude that diamond particles grew under 2.5 kPa chamber pressure with 2 and 5 minutes seeding time exhibit better SiV photoluminescent property.

To further investigate the effects of pressure on the microstructure and SiV PL, we synthesized diamond particles on optical fiber with chamber pressure increasing to 3.5 and 4.5 kPa, respectively. Fig. 5 displays their PL and corresponding Raman spectra. The insets are their SEM morphologies. Fig. 5(a) indicates that the sample

synthesized at 3.5 kPa exhibits a relatively weak SiV photoluminescence since it mainly consists of TPA and graphite with a small amount of diamond content. Its inset SEM shows that spherical-shape particles are inhomogeneously distributed on fiber surface with size around hundreds of nanometers to several micrometers. The SiV ZPL position is around 739 nm with FWHM about 8 nm. This indicates that 3.5 kPa pressure results in relatively poor SiV photoluminescent property.

Fig. 5(b) shows the PL, Raman and SEM morphology of samples synthesized under 4.5 kPa. The PL spectrum shows the absence of SiV photoluminescence peak. And their corresponding Raman spectrum indicates that the sample consists of non-diamond phase like TPA and graphite with few of diamond contents. Some flake-shape particles with size about 800 nm to 1 μm are observed in the samples. Comparing Fig. 5(a) and (b), we can conclude that high chamber pressure of 4.5 kPa is not suitable to deposit SiV center contained diamond particle on fiber.

Our results show that it is difficult to prepare diamond particles on optical fiber with single SiV center in our present study. By further adjusting the experiment parameters, like the controlled doping of silicon during diamond deposition, few SiV color centers in diamond will be achieved. Our results supply a crucial step toward the integration of optical fiber and SiV centered diamond particles.

4. Conclusion

In summary, by adjusting the deposition parameters in the CVD process, we synthesized the SiV photoluminescent diamond particles on the fiber surface. The effects of chamber pressure on the microstructural and photoluminescent properties of diamond particles are investigated. The results show that samples synthesized under 2.5 kPa exhibit better SiV photoluminescent property. The particles with size around 200 to 400 nm were uniformly distributed on the fiber surface. With chamber pressure increasing to 3.5 kPa, diamond quality becomes worse and non-diamond phase contents increase, weakening the SiV photoluminescent intensity. In the case of 4.5 kPa, the contents of diamond continuously decrease with increased TPA and graphite, so that the synthesized particles exhibit no SiV photoluminescence.

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Figure captions:

Fig. 1 SEM graphs of diamond particles on fiber surface under different seeding times of 0, 2, 5 and 15 minutes with the same chamber pressure as 1.6 kPa and deposition time of 20 min, which is named 1.6T0, 1.6T2, 1.6T5 and 1.6T15, respectively.

Fig. 2 (a) PL and (b) Raman spectra of diamond particles on fiber surface under different seeding times of 0, 2, 5 and 15 minutes with the same chamber pressure as 1.6 kPa and deposition time of 20 min, which is named 1.6T0, 1.6T2, 1.6T5 and 1.6T15, respectively.

Fig. 3 SEM graphs of diamond particles on fiber surface under different seeding times of 0, 2, 5 and 15 minutes with the same chamber pressure as 2.5 kPa and deposition time of 20 min, which is named 2.5T0, 2.5T2, 2.5T5 and 2.5T15, respectively.

Fig.4 (a) PL and (b) Raman spectra of diamond particles on fiber surface under different seeding times of 0, 2, 5 and 15 minutes with the same chamber pressure as 2.5 kPa and deposition time of 20 min, which is named 2.5T0, 2.5T2, 2.5T5 and 2.5T15, respectively.

Fig. 5 The PL and corresponding Raman spectra inset with SEM graph of diamond particles synthesized under the chamber pressure of (a)&(b) 3.5 kPa and (c)&(d) 4.5 kPa with 5 minutes seeding time.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

FIG. 5

